

A conceptual study for Preventive cardiology with special reference to diet and lifestyle modification.

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Abstract

Cardiovascular disease has the most prevalence of serious diseases and is a rapidly growing problem in developing countries.

In Ayurved literature available, the purpose of Ayurved is given as prevention of disease for healthy living and treating the diseases person. The same is explained in modern science as "Prevention is better than cure".

In the case of cardiology- diet, lifestyle changes are contributing to increase the risk of cardiovascular diseases. In view to avoid further complications, preventive measures should be taken in the field of cardiology with the help of Ayurved, which includes *Rasayan* therapy, *Panchakarma chitiksa*, Diet and lifestyle modification, Yoga and *Pranayam* for prevention of cardiovascular disease.

Risk factors for cardiovascular diseases includes Hypertension, obesity, Diabetes mellitus, Rheumatic disorders, most of the risk factors are related to our daily lifestyle and diet. This literature reviews includes *Rasayan* therapy, *Panchakarma* chits, Diet and lifestyle modification, Yoga and *Pranayam* for prevention of cardiovascular disease and has attempted to build a bridge between modern day to day life style and Ayurvedic lifestyle as recommended in various Ayurvedic literature.

Keywords: Cardiovascular disease; Ayurved; *Rasayan* therapy; *Panchakarma chitiksa*

1. Introduction

The above *Shloka* explains the purpose of Ayurved, Prevention of disease for healthy living and treating the diseased person.^[1]

Heart is one of the vital organ (*Trimarmas*) in humans and Ayurved.

Cardiovascular disease comprise of a group of disease of the heart and the vascular system. The major conditions are ischemic heart disease, hypertension and congenital heart disease. Rheumatic heart disease continues to be an important health problem in many developing countries.^[3]

Now a days, diet and life style pattern of whole population across the world had changed. Changes in diet and lifestyle pattern, lack of exercise, increased stress factor, environmental changes had increased the incidence of cardiovascular disease.

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In the case of cardiology for preventing the disease Ayurved has explained *Rasayan* therapy, *Panchakarma Chikitsa*, diet and lifestyle modification, *Yoga* and *Pranayam*. In cardiovascular diseases Ayurved has its literature for the cause, pathophysiology, types, preventive measures, treatment.^[5]

Aims and Objectives

- To assess the role of Ayurved in prevention of cardiovascular diseases.
- To assess the Ayurvedic literature in various cardiovascular diseases.
- To assess *Ahara, Vihara, Yoga, Rasayan, Panchakarma* having role in preventing various cardiovascular diseases.

2. Material and methods

Ayurvedic Classical books, research papers and journals.

2.1. Hridayam

Ayurved has considered hridayam has a vital organ and a center (mulasthanam) for *pranavahstrotas, rasavahstrotas, manovahstrotas* Oja.

According to *Ayurved*, *hridayam* is a maternal organ and is formed from *Khapha, Rakta, Mansa, Dhatu*

Hridyam is the *sthana* of *Vyana Vayu, Sadhakapitta, Avalambakkapha, ojha* which makes the heart to pump to circulate the *Dhatu*s.

So any vitiation in the *dosha* during its formation can lead to various diseases.

2.1.1. Hridayaroga

Table 1 Co-relation of symptoms of Hridoga given in Ayurveda and Modern science

	Symptoms of Hridroga ⁵	Symptoms of Cardiovascular diseases ⁶
1	<i>Vaivarnya</i> (Cyanosis)	Dyspnoea
2	<i>Murcha</i> (Syncope)	Orthopnoea
3	<i>Jwara</i> (Fever)	Chest pain
4	<i>Kasa</i> (cough)	Oedema
5	<i>Hikka</i> (Hiccough)	Palpitation
6	<i>Shwasa</i> (Dyspnoea)	Cheyne stokes breathing
7	<i>MukhaVairasya</i> (better taste)	Anorexia
8	<i>Trishna</i> (Excessive Thirst)	Vomiting
9	<i>Pramoha</i> (Stupor)	Syncope
10	<i>Chardi</i> (Vomiting)	Fatigue
11	<i>Kaphoutklesha</i> (Nausea)	
12	<i>Urshoola</i> (Chest pain)	
13	<i>Aruchi</i> (Anorexia)	

2.2. Risk Factors for cardiovascular diseases

- High Blood pressure (Hypertension)
- High Blood Cholesterol
- Uncontrolled Diabetes
- Obesity and Overweight
- Smoking
- Physical Inactivity
- Gender (males are at higher risk)

- Heredity
- Race
- Age
- Contributing Risk factors
- Stress
- Sex Hormones
- Birth control pills
- Excessive Alcohol intake

2.3. Prevention

Various preventive measures are mentioned in available literature,

- *Rasayan* therapy
- *Panchakarma* therapy
- *Yoga* therapy
- Diet and lifestyle modification.

2.3.1. *Rasayan* therapy

Various types of *Yogas* are prescribed after *shodhana* therapy, it helps in maintaining the immunity and thus one can prevent various diseases.

Use of *Hridya gana*⁷

Hridyagana: Amra, Amrataka, Lakucha, Karamarda, Vrksamla, Amlavetasa, Kuvala, Badara, Dadima, Matulunga.

2.3.2. *Panchakarma* therapy

Performing various *Panchakarma* modalities like *Snehan* (oleation), *Swedan* (fomentation), *Vaman* (emetic therapy), *virechana* (purgation therapy), *Basti* (medicated enema therapy), *nasya* (inhalation therapy) are useful in preventing various cardiovascular diseases by treating dyslipidemia, obesity.

A very specialized *Hridbasti* a type of *snehan* (oleation therapy) and *Swedan* (fomentation) provides bal to *Hridya*, *strotas*.

2.3.3. *Yoga* therapy

Various *asanas* are explained by *acharyas*, which are useful providing *bal* to *hridya* and *strotas*, these include

- *Sukhasan*
- *Tadasan*
- *Uthanasan*
- *Padangushtasan*
- *Adhomukhasan*
- *Sarvasan*
- *Suptapadangushtasan*

This can be done regularly.

2.3.4. *Diet and lifestyle modification*

Diet modification

The above *shloka* in *charaksutrasthan* explains that, humans (cell) are dependent on food for their living and also diseases are dependent on what food we eat.⁹

To improve metabolic conversion (anabolism) use of *deepen* and *pachandravyas* like *Hingu*, *Ajawain*, *lasun*.

- Plenty of raw or cooked salads or vegetables like Cabbage, Cauliflower, Cucumber, Carrots, etc.

- Vegetables prepared with no or very little oil e.g., green leafy vegetables like Spinach, Radish, Bringal, lady's finger, cabbage, cauliflower, chapatti without oil, Skimmed milk.
- Controlled use of MUFA like olive, Groundnut oil, mustard oil.
- Controlled use of PUFA like Sunflower oil.
- Avoid Saturated fat like Dalda, Butter.
- Reuse of oil for frying is not allowed as it contains more free radicals.
- For fibers eat leafy vegetables and eat fruits and avoid fruit juices.
- Fibers reduce the cholesterol absorption.

Lifestyle modification

- Cessation of smoking

One the best thing one can do for self is avoiding tobacco in any of the form available.

- Weight reduction

Obesity is a large contributor for many of the cardiovascular disease.

- Daily exercise

Exercise (*Vyayama*)

The *karma* which brings fatigueness like feeling is called as *Vyayama*.¹⁰ *Vyayama* helps in reducing the levels of Serum Cholesterol, relieves hypertension and improves overall general Physiology of the body. Potential Cardio-protective effects of regular physical activity

Table 2 Type II diabetes and Hypertension control

Pressure			
Reduces adiposity	increases social support	decreases fibrinogen	Decreases endothelial dysfunction
Increases insulin Sensitivity		decreases blood viscosity	Increases nitric oxide
Decreases inflammation			
Anti-Atherosclerotic	Psychologic	Anti-Thrombolic	Anti Ischemic
Improves lipids	decreases depression	decreases platelet adhesiveness	Decreases myocardial O2 demand
Lowers blood	decreases stress	increases fibrinolysis	Decreases coronary flow

Type II diabetes and Hypertension control.

Strict diabetic diet and good glycaemic control by insulin or OHA along with good control over hypertension reduces the risk of cardiovascular diseases.

3. Discussion

The increase incidence of the cardiovascular diseases all over the world is due to the faulty diet pattern & life style, Obesity, & uncontrolled Diabetes mellitus. Uncontrolled hypertension & dyslipidaemia are the common risk factors for the cardiovascular diseases. Role of *Ayurveda* in the prevention and cure of the cardiovascular diseases is very systematic and good manner. In *Ayurveda Rasayana* therapy, *Panchakarma* therapy, *Yoga* therapy, Diet and lifestyle modification (*Ahara, Vihara*) are described which have good role in preventing cardiovascular diseases. Different researches have been showed that *Ayurveda* drugs have effective role in cardiovascular diseases. If someone adopt the diet pattern, life style according to the *Ayurveda* it can be helpful in the decrease the incidence of cardiovascular diseases. In text of *Ayurveda* there are number of drugs, formulation are described which have very effective result on the cardiovascular diseases.

4. Conclusion

In *Ayurveda Ahara, Vihara, Yoga, Rasayana* are described which have good role in preventing & cardiovascular diseases. The prevention of cardiovascular diseases can be done successfully in *Ayurved*.

Compliance with ethical standards

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